

Accelerated Aging of FRP in Hot-Water by Ultrasonic
Vibration Technique

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the durability of FRP in the long term immersion test in hot water. The materials tested are glassfiber reinforced unsaturated polyester (GRP) laminates. Two kinds of matrixs, orthophthalic polyester and bisphenol polyester, are employed in order to examine the effects of matrix on degradation of GRP.

The changes of the absorbed water and mechanical properties of GRP laminate are examined during the immersion test in hot water. At the same time, the acoustic emission tests are carried out for monitoring initiation and growth of damage in composites. The relation between the reduction in mechanical properties and damage propagation of FRP is investigated to clarify the degradation mechanism of the composite. Furthermore, the accelerated immersion test by the aid of ultrasonic cleaning technique are applied to the composite laminate, and the availability of this method is proved.

INTRODUCTION

The study on the environmental effects is presently being of great interest in the effective design of GRP laminate. The possibility that absorbed water may lead to a reduction in mechanical properties by weakening the bond between the fillers and matrix or by plasticizing the matrix has been acknowledged [1][2]. As the data of the long term exposure test are often difficult to obtain, attempts are often made to simulate the effects of long term exposure to water by accelerating the aging process by immersion in hot, usually boiling water [3]. However, this method is poor effective for the long term immersion test in hot water. The new method on accelerated aging of GRP in hot water was proposed in this paper, where the aging of GRP is accelerated by repeating

the immersion in hot water and ultrasonic cleaning in water at lower temperature alternately. In ultrasonic cleaning, the shock waves produced by cavitation hit the GRP surfaces in contact with water, and, in combination with acoustic streaming phenomena, cause a highly effective scouring action. Therefore, the shock waves of ultrasonic cleaning are considered to accelerate degradation of the bond between the fibers and matrix. In order to examine the effects of absorbed water on the mechanical properties of GRP, the weight change, the residual strength and the rigidity reduction of the samples were measured during immersion test in hot water.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

GRP used in this experiment were E-glassfibre reinforced thermosetting plastics. The reinforcement was continuous E-glassfibre mat with 3 plies, and the matrixes are two kinds of unsaturated polyester resin, that is, orthophthalic type(Ortho-type) and bisphenol type(Bisphenol-type). The molding conditions of these materials are summarized in Table 1.

The square shaped panels were fabricated by matched-die molding method. The side of the panel was 300mm. The specimens were cut out from seven places in this panel. The configuration of the specimen was 300mm in length, 30mm in width and 3mm in thickness. The coating of silicon resin was done at the edge surface for the sake of prevention of water absorption.

Table 1 Molding conditions of the mechanicals tested.

Resin	Orthophthalic UP	Bisphenol UP
Reinforcement	Continuous Glass Mat	
Molding Method	MMD	
After Cure	90 °C, 1 h r.	
Numbers of ply	3	
Elastic Modulus (MPa)	12460	11030
Tensile Strength (MPa)	94.6	88.1

The water immersion tests were conducted at 80°C with the instrument in which the hot water was circulated by a pump for making the temperature uniform. The periods of immersion in this experiment are shown in Table 2. The rates at which water was absorbed by the specimens were determined by periodic weighing. The tensile tests after various immersion tests were carried out by the Instron type testing machine with constant cross-head speed of 0.5mm/min. under room temperature in order to examine the residual strength and the rigidity reduction of the dry specimens. Acoustic emission (AE) test was conducted simultaneously in order to monitor the damage propagation of GRP. Fig.1 shows the specimen configuration and the locations of AE sensors and a strain gage. The amplitude distributions of AE were measured at each tensile test.

Table 2 Experimental conditions

Kind of Test	Ordinary	Accelerated
Exposure time (hr.)	0, 3, 10, 30, 100, 300 1000, 2000, 3000	3, 10, 30, 100, 300 1000, 3000
Ultrasonic cleaning time (min.)	0	5
Temperature of hot water(°C)	80	

Fig.1 Shape and dimension of specimen.

Furthermore, the accelerated immersion tests with various periods illustrated in Table 2 were carried out by combining the immersion in hot water with ultrasonic cleaning in water at room temperature. The ultrasonic cleaning was conducted in the water chamber for 5 minutes every exposure time as shown Table 2. The ultrasonic frequency was around 20000Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is well known that the degradations of the resin matrix and the interface and the change of the specimen weight may arise during the immersion test in water. This weight change is considered to be produced by the increases of the absorbed water and the dissolved matrix in water. The former increases the specimen weight and the latter decreases, as shown in Fig.2. In this figure, M_g shows the weight gain by means of the absorbed water and is calculated by

$$M_g = (W_w - W_d) / W_o$$

,where W_w is the wet specimen weight after immersion test and W_d is that of the dried specimen, and W_o is the original dried specimen weight. M_l shows the weight loss by means of the dissolved matrix and is given by

$$M_l = (W_o - W_d) / W_o$$

Therefore, the apparent weight gain, M_a , can be given by

$$M_a = M_g - M_l.$$

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of weight gain(M_a),weight loss(M_l) and apparent weight gain(M_a).

Fig.3 Change of apparent weight gain (M_a) in ordinary immersion test.

Ordinary Immersion Test

Fig.3 shows the relationship between the apparent weight gain, M_a , and the exposure time for both types of specimen in the exposure test. Fig.4 shows the variation in the weight gain M_g and weight loss M_l with the exposure time for the specimen of Ortho-type, and Fig.5 shows that of the Bisphenol-type. It is found in these figures that W_g of Ortho-type specimen is much larger than that of Bisphenol-type and W_l 's of both types are close, and then W_a of Ortho-type is very different from that of Bisphenol-type. These behaviours suggest that the physical degradation by swelling in Ortho-type is very large in comparison with the chemical degradation by hydrosis of resin matrix and this tendency in the case of Bisphenol-type is small.

Fig.4 Changes of weight gain(M_g) and weight loss(M_l) in ordinary immersion test (Ortho-type).

Fig.5 Changes of weight gain(M_g) and weight loss(M_l) in ordinary immersion test (Bisphenol-type).

Figs. 6 and 7 show the variation in the rigidity reduction and residual strength with exposure time for two types of specimen, respectively. The elastic modulus and the tensile strength in vertical axis are normalized by the those of the original dried specimen. It is to be noted that the reductions of the mechanical properties in Ortho-type are larger than these of Bisphenol-type and the physical and chemical deductions of the specimens have direct effects upon the mechanical reductions.

Fig.6 Relation between retention of tensile modulus and exposure time.

Fig.7 Relation between retention of tensile strength and exposure time.

Accelerated Immersion Test

In the accelerated immersion test, the effect of exposure time on the apparent weight gain, M_a , is shown in Fig.8. Figs. 9 and 10 show the effect of exposure time on the weight gain, M_g , and the weight loss, M_l , in both types of the specimen. Comparing the experimental results of the ordinary test in Figs. 3,4 and 5 with those of the accelerated test, there are very small difference in Ortho-type specimen and considerable differences in Bisphenol-type at the exposure time above 1000hrs. Therefore, it is recognized that the ultrasonic cleaning technique has significant effects upon Bisphenol-type specimen.

Fig.8 Change of apparent weight gain(Ma) in accelerated immersion test.

Fig.9 Changes of weight gain(Mg) and weight loss(M₁) in accelerated immersion test (Ortho-type).

Fig.10 Changes of weight gain(Mg) and weight loss(M₁) in accelerated immersion test (Bisphenol-type).

Fig.11 (a) and (b) show the typical tensile load-displacement curves of Bisphenol-type in the both type of immersion test. It is to be noted that the curves in the ordinary test decrease in size at the time above 2000 hours, and these of the accelerated test at the time above 1000hours.

Fig.11 Typical load-displacement curves.
 (a) Ordinary immersion test
 (b) Accelerated immersion test

Figs. 12, 13 and 14 show the retentions of the normalized elastic modulus, tensile strength and fracture strain of Bisphenol-type in both immersion tests, respectively. It is found in these figures that there aren't any differences in the reduction of the elastic modulus by two types of test. However, there are considerable differences in the tensile strength and fracture strain by both tests at time of 1000hrs. Therefore, the failure mechanism of GRP is proved to turn to brittle by weakening the interface and plasticizing the resin matrix. These behaviors suggest that the ultrasonic cleaning technique is successful for acceleration of the immersion test.

The results of AE tests are shown in order to clarify the effect of ultrasonic vibration on the fracture mechanism of GRP. Fig.15(a),(b) and (c) show the typical AE amplitude distribution in the original dry specimen, the ordinary and accelerated immersed specimens at the exposure time of 1000hrs. These specimens are all Bisphenol-type. The original specimen has a lot of AE event counts with low amplitude and a few with middle amplitude. As the immersion time increases, AE event counts with low amplitude decrease and those of middle amplitude increase. AE event counts with high amplitude decrease at the time above 1000hrs in the

accelerated test. These phenomena indicate that the correlation between the AE amplitude distribution and the retention of the strength and the fracture strain is considerable large, and AE test is a usefull method for monitoring the durability of GRP in immersion test.

Fig.12 Relation between retention of tensile modulus of Bisphenol-type and exposure time.

Fig.13 Relation between retention of tensile strength of Bisphenol-type and exposure time.

Fig.14 Relation between retention of fracture strain of Bisphenol-type and exposure time.

Fig.15 Distribution of AE amplitude.
 (a)Original dry specimen
 (b)Ordinary immersed specimen
 at 1000hr
 (c)Accelerated immersed
 specimen at 1000hr

CONCLUSION

This paper is concerned with the durability of GRP in the two types of immersion test in hot water. The main results obtained are summarized as follows;

- 1) The mechanism of the weight change of absorbed water was clarified by measuring the weight gain by absorbed water and the weight loss by the dissolved matrix.
- 2) The proposed method on the accelerated aging of GRP by ultrasonic cleaning technique was proved to be useful.

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